

Factors of Customer Retention in Telecom Industry

Anas Bhatti¹, Rameen Atif²

¹Lecturer, Iqra University Karachi, anasbhatti007@gmail.com

²Lecturer, Iqra University Karachi

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to examine the impact of product quality, customer service, price, advertisement CRM on customer retention in telecom industry of Pakistan. One hundred and ten people of different professional in Lahore asked questions about customer retention (CR), product quality (PQ), customer service (CS), price (P), advertisement (A) and CRM (CRM). One hundred and ten participants were randomly sampled with return rate at 100 percent. The data that was collected from the different professionals was entered in the SPSS software. Different tests were applied to the collected data. The results show the product quality (PQ), customer service (CS), price (P), advertisement (A) and CRM (CRM) have direct effect on the customer retention. Customer retention is improved if all the above factors improved and vice versa. The results revealed positive relationship dependent variable and its independent variables. There also some limitations that are give in this study and which will helpful for the future study.

Keywords: Customer retention, product quality, customer service, price, advertisement and CRM.

Introduction

This study is mainly revolving around the problem that customer's are not retaining with the company's in Pakistan. Customers change their products, brand or services due to company. Or when they change their required product or services but the company is not providing that product or service, so ultimately the customer has to change the company. This was a broader term that why customer leave the companies. But in this whole scenario, there are many other reasons to change the company. Particularly the telecom industry is the best example for it. Customer has a lot of choices to adopt a suitable company's on the basis of many reasons. The customer's have choices, so it wants more satisfaction. It always goes for only its benefit. A reason to not retain swath company is this that, it is varying easy for a customer to change the company or switch the company from one to another. Their is price war in telecom industry. The company's are attracting the customer through reducing their prices. This factor is also required to retain the previous customers. Now companies are realizing that customers are their productive and profit generating asst. So the companies have to retain their existing customers as well as attracting new customers. Companies have realized this need and now moving to adopt procedures of CRM (Customer Relationship Management). In this study we will discuss the main problem that is customer are not retaining with companies.

Particularly the telecom industry is the best example for it. Customer has a lot of choices to adopt a suitable company's on the basis of many reasons. The customer's have choices, so it wants more satisfaction. It always goes for only its benefit. A reason to not retain with company is this that, it

is varying easy for a customer to change the company or switch the company from one to another. There is price war in telecom industry. The company's are attracting the customer through reducing their prices. This factor is also required to retain the previous customers. Now companies are realizing that customers are their productive and profit generating asst. So the companies have to retain their existing customers as well as attracting new customers. So this study describes the how the factors product quality (PQ), customer service (CS), price (P), advertisement (A) and CRM (CRM) are affecting the customer retention (CR) in the telecom industry of Pakistan.

This study is mainly revolving around the problem that customer's are not retaining with the telecom companies in Pakistan. Customers change their products, brand or services due to dissatisfaction from the telecom companies of Pakistan. Or when they change their required product or services but the company is not providing that product or service, so ultimately the customer has to change the company. This was a broader term that why customer leave the companies. But in this whole scenario there are many other reasons to change the company.

1. The purpose of this study is to make sure the realization of customer retention that it is so important for telecom companies of Pakistan.
2. This study can be used by the any type of organizations to get know the importance of customer retention.
3. This study provides a platform to the new incomers in Pakistan of telecom industry.
4. This study investigates the strength and the weaknesses of telecom industry in Pakistan.
5. This study gives an opportunity for improvement of customer retention in telecom industry of Pakistan.

This research will enlarge our mind to understand the customer retention in telecom industry of Pakistan and also add knowledge that how the factors of product quality, customer service, price, advertisement and CRM affect it.

Firstly, this study is conducted to check the customer retention in telecom industry of Pakistan. So this study provides a gateway to the decision makers of Pakistani telecom industry. One important thing that I would like to describe here that there is no study on this topic has been conducted in Pakistan. Most of research on this topic has been conducted in the developed countries like Europe and that cannot be applicable in the countries like Pakistan.

Do the Factors of customer retention have impact on retaining the customer of telecom industry in Pakistan?

What is the impact of customer retention in telecom industry of Pakistan?

Is the product quality and customer retention are related to each other.

What is effect of price, customer service, advertisement and CRM on customer retention?

Literature Review

1. In their 2002 study, Moon-Kom Kim and colleagues explored the factors influencing customer retention in Korea's telecommunication industry. They identified four key determinants: switching costs, interpersonal relationships, attractiveness of alternatives, and service recovery, treating these as independent variables with customer retention as the dependent variable. The study focused on current mobile users, gathering data from high school students, college and graduate students, and working professionals, amounting to a sample size of 323. Statistical analyses, including factor analysis, confidence analysis, and regression analysis, were conducted using SPSS 10.0.

2. The research aimed to understand the impact of switching barriers on customer retention, examining the connection between customer satisfaction and these barriers in the mobile communication service sector. The study first reviewed and empirically tested the relationship between customer retention and switching barriers. It highlighted the lack of comprehensive studies on the role of switching barriers, noting that only partial aspects had been previously examined. This paper contributed by reviewing factors like switching costs, interpersonal relationships, attractiveness of alternatives, and service recovery, and how they influence customer retention. It also examined the specific structure and role of switching barriers in the service industry, noting the industry-specific differences.

3. The theoretical contribution of this paper was the detailed analysis of the relationship between customer retention and switching barriers. It underscored the importance of factors that enhance the bond between service providers and customers within these barriers. The study also suggested practical improvements, such as reducing switching costs to lessen consumer risk and dependency and enhancing interpersonal relationships to provide better customer service.

4. Separately, Su-Chao Chang and colleagues in 2006 integrated the American Customer Satisfaction Model (ACSM) in their research conducted in China. They used seven determinants for customer satisfaction: perceived quality, perceived expectations, perceived value, perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness, customer complaints, and customer loyalty, treating these as independent variables with customer satisfaction as the dependent one. The study, which had a sample size of 274, utilized questionnaires for data collection and employed seven model-fit measures to evaluate the model's effectiveness.

My suggestions in this respect are that we should develop questionnaires to determine the customer satisfaction. Because in questionnaire we observe the customers by face to face and check better. There are other techniques to assess the customer satisfaction. We should not check the customer satisfaction by email as the above author has done. We should also interview in this respect which is another important tool to assess to customer satisfaction. Observation is another tool which also be used to measure the customer satisfaction. Kevin R. Parker et al (2009) studied The Impact of Inaccurate Color on Customer Retention and CRM. He used the color as independent variable and customer retention and CRM as dependent variable. The sample size is 300 students of different colleges. The study is conducted in USA. The tool used in this article is questionnaire to get data from different people.

Treiblmaier et al (2003) studied the How Companies Utilize Web Sites to Strengthen Customer Relationships. He used the quality, quantity, interactivity as independent variables while customer relationships as dependent variable. The sample size is 155 and the tool which is used for collecting the data that is observation.

The study was conducted in Austria. The SPSS is used for analysis for the variables. The tool that is used for analysis is descriptive analysis. The results are that quality, quantity and interactivity have a great effect on customer relationships. We improve the customer relationships by improving the above factors. My suggestions in this research are that use the questionnaires to collect the data and sample size should be increased.

Ofir Turel et al (2004) studied the Satisfaction with mobile services in Canada. The following

variables are used in this article.

1. Perceived Quality
2. Perceived Value
3. Perceived Expectations
4. Repurchase Likelihood
5. Customer Complaints
6. Price Tolerance
7. Customer Satisfaction

The last one is dependent while the remaining is independent variables. The study was conducted in the first quarter of 2004. The sample size is 210 of current mobile users. SPSS used for the analysis. The tool which used for analysis is graphs. The questionnaires were used to collect data. The study was conducted in Canada. Findings are that all the independent variables have a great effect on satisfaction of mobile users. We increase the value of all the independent variables the satisfaction of mobile users will be much more. My suggestion is crm, price, advertisement will also be improved for the better customer satisfaction.

PEZ V. et al (2008) studied the Negative Effects of Loyalty Programs in France. The following variables are used in the study; Loyalty programs as dependent variable while the negative emotions, churn, and mobile communications as independent variables. This study was conducted in France. The questionnaires were used to collect the data from the peoples. The sample size is 232. Two questionnaires were administrated among two independent samples. Finding is that the quantitative study shows that negative emotions experienced with loyalty programs. My suggestions are that the managers should pay particular attention to the identification of possible incidents related to their loyalty program.

The sample size is 132 and sample is taken from a new university in Nigeria. Questionnaires were used to collect the data from the staffs of the university. This research is conducted in Nigeria to improve the customer service in the telecommunication sectors of Nigeria. Edward Faber et al (2003) studied Balancing Requirements for Customer Value of Mobile Services. He used the following variables in his study Security, Quality of service, System integration and Accessibility. The customer value is dependent variable while the security, quality of service, system integration and accessibility are the independent variables. This study is conducted in UK. The sample size is 502 and the data is collected from the different locations of London. Questionnaires are used for the data collecting. Results are that the customer value increases the as the independent variables improved and while versa. Suggestions are that the research should discuss the business model. The organizations should develop the service value to their customers.

Findings are that the price and service are very important for customer retention in telecom industry. They directly affect the customer retention in telecom industry. Suggestions are the companies of telecom industry in Sir Linka should take data from corporate and non- corporate sector. He used the customer retention as dependent variable while customer treatment programs were used as independent variables in the study. This study was conduct in china for a telecom company. He calculated the customer retention through customer intelligence. The sample size used in this study is 500 people and from whom data was collected for research purpose. Questionnaires were used to collect the data from the sample size. The tool that is used for data analysis is the customer

retention system based on intelligence was introduced.

PEZ V. et al (2008) studied the negative effects of customer loyalty programs in French mobile sector. He used the loyalty programs as dependent variables and satisfaction, intentions, word of mouth as independent variables. This research is conducted in France for the loyalty programs of mobile sectors. The sample size is taken from the following people of France.

Russell S. Winer (2001) studied the Customer Relationship Management as a factor of customer retention. He used the two variables for the study. He used Customer relationship management as dependent variable and the customer retention as independent variable. This research is conducted in America. Questionnaire is used for the data collecting. The data is collected from the student of universities of New York. Data is collected from both male and female. The technique which used for the data analysis is LCV.

By Dr Rhian Silvestro (2000) He used the customer satisfaction as dependent variable and the customer service, small business service, wholesale service as the independent variables. This study is conducted in Singapore. Interview is used for the data collecting method. The sample size is taken through different European countries for the interpretation of results. The tool that is used for the data analysis is longitudinal analysis.

Zurich (2005) used the retention strategies as dependent variable while customer profitability as the independent variables in his study. This study is conducted in Switzerland. Data is collected through Customer transaction systems. The sample size is taken 50 multinational companies in Switzerland. The tool that is used for data analysis is SOM.

Glovera (2004) studied the role of the customer loyalty in the mobile market of America. He used the customer loyalty as dependent variable and the willingness, retention are used as independent variables. This study is done in America. The data is collected through interview and the sample size is 12,000 people through the nine countries of the world. The results willingness and the retention directly affect the customer loyalty. Suggestion is that the sample size must be increased for the better result.

Bob Thompson (2005) studied the loyalty connection through the customer connection. He used the two variables, loyalty connection is dependent and the customer connection is as the independent variable. This study is done in Italy. Data is collected through interviews. The sample size is 600 businessmen of Italy. Results show the customer connection directly affects the loyalty.

Lori K. Molinari(1999) investigated the Customer Service and its Effects on Customer Retention and Defection. He used the customer retention as the dependent variable and the service quality, behavioral quality as the independent variables in his research. This research is conducted in Germany. The sample size is 223. Questionnaires are used for the data collection method. .

Richard Lee et al (2001) studied the THE LOYALTY OF PREPAID AND POSTPAID MOBILE CUSTOMER. They used the loyalty as the dependent variable while the Service, attitude, switching costs, mobile telecommunications are used as the independent variables in their research. This study is conducted in Singapore. The data is collected through questionnaires.

In this era of intense competition, it is very important for any service company to understand that

merely acquiring customers is not sufficient because there is a direct link between customer retention over time and profitability & growth. Customer retention to a great extent depends on service quality and customer satisfaction. It also depends on the ability of the organization to encourage customers to complain and then recover when things go wrong. Complaints are natural part of any service activity as mistakes are an unavoidable feature of all human endeavor and thus also of service recovery.

Theoretical Framework

Methodology

To find the results of customer retention in the telecom industry of Pakistan, I have collected the data for the customer retention through five variables, product quality (PQ), customer service (CS), price (P), advertisement (A) and CRM (CRM). Questionnaires were employed as the primary tool for gathering data on customer retention. As noted by Bolly in 1999, lecturers frequently encounter questionnaires, ranging from standard end-of-year course evaluations to those utilized in research contexts. It's crucial to recognize that constructing a questionnaire is a multi-stage process. This process starts with identifying the specific elements to be investigated and culminates in the interpretation of the findings, as highlighted by Goley in 1997.

The responses are gathered in a standardized way, so questionnaires are more objective, certainly more so than interviews.

Generally it is relatively quick to collect information using a questionnaire. However in some situations they can take a long time not only to design but also to apply and analyse. Potentially information can be collected from a large portion of a group. This potential is not often realised, as returns from questionnaires are usually low. However return rates can be dramatically improved if the questionnaire is delivered and responded to in class time. Questionnaires, like many evaluation methods occur after the event, so participants may forget important issues.

Questionnaires are standardized so it is not possible to explain any points in the questions that participants might misinterpret. This could be partially solved by piloting the questions on a small group of students or at least friends and colleagues. It is advisable to do this anyway.

Open-ended questions can generate large amounts of data that can take a long time to process and analyze. One way of limiting this would be to limit the space available to students so their responses are concise or to sample the students and survey only a portion of them.

Respondents may answer superficially especially if the questionnaire takes a long time to complete. The common mistake of asking too many questions should be avoided.

Students may not be willing to answer the questions.

Each method has some advantages and disadvantages but try to minimize the errors.

The data is collected from different people of Lahore which includes students, businessman, and professional and randomly people. The data is collected from 110 people for the research purpose of telecom industry of Pakistan. The data is taken randomly from Lahore.

In this study, SPSS 16.0 software was employed to examine the relationships among various variables. Data were gathered on six variables, including customer retention (CR) as the dependent variable, and product quality (PQ), customer service (CS), price (P), advertisement (A), and Customer Relationship Management (CRM) as independent variables. Thomas (2000) suggests that questionnaires are an economical method for data collection. We utilized SPSS software for data analysis, specifically for examining ego-centered networks. SPSS is renowned in the social sciences as one of the most frequently used software packages, playing a significant role in empowering self-conducted research with individuals as distinct units of analysis (Wellman, 1998). However, quantitative analysis of ego-centered network data presents more complexities than traditional survey research that focuses on individuals as units of analysis. Network analysts are required to manage multiple types of information simultaneously (Campbell and Lee, 1991).

Then we compute the variables of the research. Five questions of each variable are merged into a single question in order to find the better results.

There are two data analysis tools descriptive and inferential statistics. In descriptive we apply Frequency, Percentage, Mean and Standard deviation. In inferential statistics we apply Correlation.

Data Analysis

This chapter details the data analysis and findings of the study. Initially, a summary of demographic data is presented, followed by descriptive statistics for each variable. The research encompassed various sectors of the general economy, with a sample size of 110 respondents. All selected participants (n = 110) completed the survey. The analysis of the data involved examining demographic summaries, descriptive statistics, regression analyses, scatter plots, and correlations. This analysis was facilitated by the use of the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS), version 16.0.

Data screening, an integral part of our process, involved condensing large datasets into histograms or frequency distributions, enabling calculations such as mean values. Data collection was achieved through questionnaires, with concerted efforts made to ensure a complete 100% response rate from participants. SPSS was then employed for the interpretation of these results. Each of the results will be discussed in detail in the following sections.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.809	5

The reliability of the data for the five questions related to the customer retention variable is indicated by a value of .809, which exceeds the threshold of .7. This suggests that the data is dependable and suitable for use in further research.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.731	5

The reliability of the data pertaining to the five questions on the product quality variable is affirmed by a value of .731, surpassing the benchmark of .7. This indicates that the data is trustworthy and can be effectively utilized for subsequent research studies.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.820	5

The reliability of the data concerning the five questions related to the customer service variable is validated by a value of .820, exceeding the threshold of .7. This confirms that the data is dependable and suitable for use in future research endeavors.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.765	5

The reliability of the data for the five questions pertaining to the price variable, indicated by a value of .765, surpasses the .7 benchmark. This establishes the data's reliability, rendering it appropriate for utilization in subsequent research studies.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.747	5

The reliability score for the five questions related to the advertisement variable stands at .747, exceeding the threshold of .7. This confirms the data's reliability, making it suitable for application in further research endeavors.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.812	5

The reliability measure for the five questions concerning the CRM variable is .812, surpassing the .7 benchmark. This indicates that the data is dependable and can be confidently utilized for subsequent research studies.

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Retention	110	1.40	4.60	3.7873	.76544
Quality	110	1.60	4.40	3.7236	.68909
Service	110	1.40	4.60	3.9018	.78647
Price	110	1.40	4.20	3.8218	.76114
Advertisement	110	1.60	4.20	3.8000	.68963
CRM	110	1.40	4.60	3.7564	.76453
Valid N (listwise)	110				

The table presented summarizes the findings from the data collected, displaying responses on a 5-point scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree), with a total of 110 respondents. It includes minimum, maximum, mean, and standard deviation values for each variable. The mean value represents the average response of all respondents. Starting with retention, the mean value is 3.78, followed by the mean values of quality (3.72), service (3.9), price (3.82), advertisement (3.8), and CRM (3.75), providing an overview of the average responses. The minimum and maximum values recorded are 1.4 and 4.6, respectively. The standard deviation is used to gauge the dispersion of responses from their mean value. For instance, the price variable has a relatively low standard deviation, indicating consistent responses, whereas the service variable shows a higher standard

deviation, suggesting less consistency in responses.

Regression analysis in statistics encompasses a range of techniques used to model and examine the relationship between multiple variables. This analysis primarily focuses on how a dependent variable is influenced by one or more independent variables. Specifically, it aids in understanding how the average value of the dependent variable shifts when one independent variable is altered, keeping the other independent variables constant.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.975 ^a	.950	.948	.17454

a. Predictors: (Constant), CRM, quality, service, advertisement, price

"The R-square value is 0.950, or 95%. This indicates that 95% of the variation in the customer retention variable can be explained by changes in the independent variables. The remaining 5% of the variation is due to other factors not included in the model."

ANOVA^b

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	60.694	5	12.139	398.447	.000 ^a
	Residual	3.168	104	.030		
	Total	63.862	109			

a. Predictors: (Constant), CRM, quality, service, advertisement, price

b. Dependent Variable: retention

H0=Independent variables do not jointly affect the dependent variable.

H1=independent variable jointly affect on the dependent variable

So the significance level is less than .05 so we accept the H1 and reject the H0. So the independent variables jointly affect the dependent variable.

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-.088	.097		-.904	.368
	quality	-.147	.060	-.132	-2.452	.016
	service	-.051	.055	-.052	-.916	.362
	price	.631	.105	.628	6.005	.000
	advertisement	.553	.099	.498	5.588	.000
	CRM	.028	.077	.028	.368	.714

a. Dependent Variable: retention

This table provides the results of the regression. The objective of this study is make an equation which can be used to find the on the retention.

General equation of the regression

$$Y = c + bx$$

According to our study the equation will be

$$\text{Retention} = c + b(\text{quality}) + b(\text{service}) + b(\text{price}) + b(\text{advertisement}) + b(\text{CRM})$$

So according to this equation the result will be following.

$$\text{Retention} = -.088 - .147(\text{quality}) - .054(\text{service}) + .631(\text{price}) - .553(\text{advertisement}) - .028(\text{CRM})$$

It means that

Correlations

		Retention	Quality	Service	Price	Advertisement	CRM
Retention	Pearson Correlation	1	.864**	.858**	.967**	.957**	.905**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	110	110	110	110	110	110
Quality	Pearson Correlation	.864**	1	.816**	.894**	.910**	.836**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	110	110	110	110	110	110
Service	Pearson Correlation	.858**	.816**	1	.880**	.883**	.904**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.000	.000
	N	110	110	110	110	110	110
Price	Pearson Correlation	.967**	.894**	.880**	1	.956**	.941**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		.000	.000
	N	110	110	110	110	110	110
Advertisement	Pearson Correlation	.957**	.910**	.883**	.956**	1	.890**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000		.000
	N	110	110	110	110	110	110
CRM	Pearson Correlation	.905**	.836**	.904**	.941**	.890**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	110	110	110	110	110	110

Table 1.1 tells us about the correlation among the variables. Firstly we check the correlation between the retention and the quality variables, retention (r is .864 and p is .000) so they are correlated to each other. The retention and quality variable are also correlated to each other. Similarly, price, advertisement and the CRM are also correlated to the retention variables.

Discussion and Conclusion

The primary aim of this research is to investigate the impact of factors such as product quality, customer service, price, advertisement, and CRM on customer retention within Pakistan's telecom sector. Employing a quantitative methodology, the study gathered data from a sample of 110 participants, focusing on key determinants of customer retention in this industry. This research is

pioneering in its exploration of these variables within the context of Pakistan's telecom industry. The findings of this study are anticipated to be valuable not only for the entire telecom sector in Pakistan but also to offer practical insights for industry decision-makers. We study the articles on this topic from all over the world in order to conduct a good analysis. I have studied different articles on this topic of factors of customer retention in the telecom industry of the world. This study also provides the link between the customer retention and the independent variables. We have developed the questionnaires to collect the data of the sex variables CS, PQ, CS, P, A and the CRM. This study will provide the role of literature review for the future study telecom industry in Pakistan. So it will give a platform to the entrants of telecom industry in Pakistan. Also it will increase our knowledge in the telecom industry of Pakistan.

This study is just an attempt to find the factors of customer retention in Pakistan, which is a developing country. If we study the literature review closely then we will come to know that in the decision makers in improving the telecom industry without any research. This study provides basis to them.

We use different tests to analyses the data. The above two tests show that the independent variables affect the customer retention. We also use the scatter plot, regression and the correlations to the results among the variables. After finding all the tests, in all the tests customer retention as dependent while the product quality, customer service, price, advertisement and CRM are taken as the independent variables. The customer retention is positively related to the product quality, customer service, price, advertisement and CRM. Correlation and the regression also show the perfect relation among the variables.

These findings show that there are many factors that also play a importan role for the customer retention rather than product quality, customer service, price, advertisement and CRM in the telecom industry of Paistan. Customer retention is affected by independent variable by only 95 percent which is too much high. However in future it is possible that some other varibles also included to the study which affect the customer retention.

There are some limitations that this study is only limited to the telecommunications in Pakistan.

6.1 Conclusion:

This research on customer retention is supported in several ways. Firstly, all the companies of telecom industry provide high product quality, better customer service, better price, attractive advertisement and CRM and there no reason to leave one company to another. These finding are based on the hypothesis. If the companies provide good service to their customers then there is no reason to the leave the company. This study mostly based on literature review and a very small sample size.

Recommendation

Following thing is recommended in research.

- 1 Sample size must be increased.
- 2 Data must take throughout Pakistan.
- 3 More independent variables must be included in the research.
- 4 A comprehensive study of literature review must be done.
- 5 Different data collection method must be applied.

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